

Understanding Employee Perspectives on Corporate Social Responsibility: Insights from Public and Private Sector Enterprises in Visakhapatnam, India

Srinivasa Rao Vempali¹, Prof B Mohan Venkata Ram²,
Prof A Narasimha Rao³

¹Research Scholar, Department of Commerce & Management Studies, Andhra University
ORCID: 0009-0001-9670-3397

²Honorary Professor, Department of Commerce & Management Studies, Andhra University

³Professor, Department of Commerce & Management Studies, Andhra University

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Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in India has shifted from a purely charitable notion to a strategic element of business that connects corporate goals with societal progress. The Companies Act, 2013, which requires certain firms to allocate funds for CSR activities, has formalized these efforts and encouraged companies to embed social responsibility into their core functions. The success of such initiatives often hinges on how employees perceive them, since they play a crucial role in both implementing and promoting CSR. Examining their levels of awareness, participation, and motivation offers key insights into how well CSR values are integrated within organizations. This study investigates employee perceptions of CSR, focusing on their awareness, involvement, and views on CSR's strategic role in public and private enterprises in Visakhapatnam, India. Using a quantitative research design, primary data was gathered from employees with varying educational backgrounds, managerial positions, income ranges, and levels of work experience. Results indicate that demographic and professional factors have a significant impact on how CSR is viewed. Public sector employees tended to align more strongly with organizational CSR goals, while those in the private sector were more likely to highlight its strategic and brand-related benefits. Differences in perception were also observed across income brackets, experience levels, and job designations, revealing a complex and multifaceted understanding of CSR among employees. The findings highlight the need to strengthen employee engagement and awareness to amplify CSR's strategic value and support ethical, socially responsible business practices.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Employee Perception, Public and Private Sector, Strategic Impact, India, Organizational Engagement

Introduction

The three isolated aspects of an organization, organizational growth with sustainable development, ethical governance, and stakeholder engagement were aligned with the advent of new framework of CSR evolved from the traditional one (Maon et al., 2010). The CSR mandate that was incorporated in the Companies Act, 2013 has changed the India's corporate landscape by making CSR expenditure mandate for qualifying firms (Chhaparia & Jha, 2018). It formalized CSR and encouraged organizations to move beyond compliance, embedding social responsibility within their core business strategies. CSR is viewed as a mechanism for achieving long-term competitiveness, societal well-being and reputation enhancement (Wahyuni et al., 2024). The employees became critical internal stakeholders

who started influencing the credibility and success of CSR initiatives (Brunton et al., 2017). Whether CSR remains a symbolic obligation or becomes a deeply embedded organizational value is also determined by the perceptions, attitudes and participation of the employees (Rodrigo et al., 2019). Limited awareness and perceived superficiality of CSR effort can reduce employee engagement and weaken the intended social and ethical outcomes (Hejjas et al., 2019). However, organizational identification, job satisfaction, and loyalty are improved by the positive employee perceptions.

Literature Review

The conceptual foundation of CSR is deeply rooted in stakeholder theory, which emphasizes the responsibility of organizations toward all entities affected by their operations (Jamali, 2008). According to this perspective, a company's long-term sustainability depends on balancing the interests of diverse stakeholders both external (such as customers, communities, and governments) and internal (such as employees and shareholders). Among these, employees are regarded as vital internal stakeholders because their perceptions, commitment, and active engagement significantly determine the success and authenticity of CSR initiatives. When employees perceive CSR activities as meaningful and aligned with ethical values, they are more likely to develop trust, loyalty, and identification with their organization (Glaveli, 2021). Employees represent the organization to the external world and thus act as mediators of its social identity (Korschun, 2015). Nevertheless, detachment or cynicism among employees may be developed if CSR is viewed just as a corporate branding item. (Sheel & Vohra, 2016).

The employee engagement is an other aspect in CSR that surpasses the conventional behavioral and attitudinal phases and enters the dimensions of voluntary participation, social initiatives and ethical conduct (Valentin et al., 2015). Further studies indicate that employees experience higher levels of job satisfaction and morale in the organization that promote CSR (Kunda et al., 2019). The aspect of motivation also varies from organization to organization. It is classified into three theoretical aspects, ethical or moral responsibility, legal compliance and strategic intent (Schaltegger & Burritt, 2018).

The fact that CSR is a mandate to meet societal expectations and regulatory requirements is reflected by legal compliance motivation. The Companies Act (2013) of India structured CSR making firms to allocate at least 2% of their profits to social initiatives. This amendment incorporated legal accountability in corporate systems (Dharmapala & Khanna, 2018). In spite of the availability of wide range of literature on CSR globally, comparative regional studies focusing on employee perceptions of CSR in India remain limited.

Methodology

In this research, a survey based quantitative approach is used in the study to analyze employee perceptions of CSR in public and private enterprises in Visakhapatnam, India. Visakhapatnam, as an industrially diverse and rapidly developing region in India. It provides a unique context to study CSR across public and private enterprises. Variations in governance between traditional public organizations and corporate firms offers to study how employees perceive CSR motivations, strategic impact, and moral significance.

This research gap can be addressed by studying the perspectives of employees on CSR in these organizations and develop a route map to design organizational policy. The study also underlines the need for employee-centric CSR strategies that foster motivation, engagement and long-term sustainability. This research is conducted in two-fold. The first being descriptive provides a broad overview by assessing the levels of CSR awareness, belief and engagement and the analytical research gives the detailed analysis of employee attitudes

by correlating with demographic factors such as education, experience, managerial level and income.

Two public sector companies RINL (Visakhapatnam Steel Plant) and HPCL (Visakh Refinery) and two private sector firms Divi's Laboratories and Coromandel International are chosen for this research study for their strong workforce diversity and strong CSR performance. A total of 400 employees, using random sampling method, representing all management levels were surveyed to ensure balanced and reliable data. The primary data was a structured questionnaire. A five-point Likert scale is used to measure employees' perceptions and engagement in CSR initiatives with a range from strong disagreement to strong agreement.

The questionnaire's reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating strong internal consistency. Content validity was established through expert review and pilot testing with 30 respondents, ensuring clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. Data were collected through both online and in-person distribution of the questionnaire. Prior permission was obtained from the human resources departments of the selected organizations. Respondents were briefed on the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality and anonymity to encourage honest and unbiased participation. The overall response rate exceeded 90%, ensuring robust data for analysis.

Descriptive statistics including means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions—were used to summarize employee responses and establish general patterns of CSR awareness and perception. Inferential statistics including Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analysis—were applied to examine relationships between demographic variables (educational qualification, work experience, managerial cadre, annual income) and the dependent variables related to CSR awareness, involvement, and strategic perception.

The ANOVA tests determined whether significant differences existed among employee groups, while the regression models measured the strength and direction of relationships between independent and dependent variables. These methods provided empirical validation for the research hypotheses concerning employee perception and engagement with CSR initiatives. Four principal aspects representing different dimensions of employee interaction with CSR are examined in this study:

Employee Awareness of CSR

The extent to which an employee understands his or her organization's CSR policies, objectives and ongoing initiatives is referred to as employee awareness of CSR. Notable differences in CSR awareness based on sector, educational qualification, work experience, and annual income were revealed in the findings. Private sector employees exhibited relatively higher levels of CSR awareness compared to their counterparts in the public sector. Private firms such as Divi's Laboratories and Coromandel International, which often integrate CSR into their corporate identity and marketing efforts make the difference due to their proactive communication strategies and brand-oriented CSR programs. ANOVA results demonstrated statistically significant differences in CSR awareness across education and experience levels ($p < 0.05$).

A deeper understanding of CSR principles and their organizational relevance is demonstrated by the employees with higher educational qualifications and longer work experience. Also, due to greater exposure to corporate communication channels and participation in strategic planning discussions, employees with higher annual income levels reported better awareness. These findings align with earlier studies suggesting that employee awareness of CSR increases with access to information, managerial exposure, and corporate

training (Carlini & Grace, 2021). However, public sector employees though familiar with the nature of CSR, often viewed it as a government-mandated activity rather than a strategic organizational process.

Employee Involvement in CSR Initiatives

The degree to which employees actively participate in planning, executing, or supporting CSR programs within their organizations is referred to as Employee involvement. Organizational encouragement plays a significant role in shaping employee participation was evident from the results. Majority of respondents perceived their organizations as moderately supportive of employee engagement in CSR activities was revealed by descriptive statistics. According to the results, a higher sense of involvement and encouragement compared to those in public enterprises was displayed by the private sector employees. These private employees revealed that CSR initiatives were linked to performance incentives, internal recognition systems and volunteer programs which are mechanisms that enhance personal commitment and motivation. Private sector organizations showing higher mean scores for employee participation confirming significant differences between sectors in employee involvement (F-values significant at $p < 0.05$). Significant predictions of involvement were also seen in educational qualification and work experience of employees highlighting that awareness and experience jointly influence the willingness to participate in CSR. The findings of this research corroborate with the earlier research establishing that when CSR activities are perceived as participatory and integrated with professional roles, the employee involvement is higher. On contrary, CSR engagement is perceived as peripheral to their job responsibilities, reflecting the procedural and hierarchical nature of decision-making by the public sector employees.

Perceived Strategic Impact of CSR

The aspect of how an employee views CSR as contributing to organizational success, brand reputation, stakeholder trust, and employee morale can be understood as the perception of CSR's strategic impact. A wide opinion stating that CSR enhances the organization's public image and fosters stronger stakeholder relationships is agreed by most of the employees in both the sectors. The results also emphasize that employees increasingly recognize CSR as more than a philanthropic endeavor especially it is seen as an integral to competitive advantage and sustainable for growth, since the mean scores related to the modules "CSR as part of business strategy" and "CSR enhancing organizational reputation" were among the highest across the questionnaire.

Regression analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between employee perception of strategic impact and their level of involvement in CSR initiatives ($\beta = 0.435$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that employees who actively participate in CSR activities are more likely to view CSR as strategically beneficial to their organization. Work experience and educational qualification emerged as significant predictors of this perception, reinforcing that experienced and educated employees possess a more nuanced understanding of CSR's strategic dimensions. The findings resonate with the theory of shared value, which posits that CSR can create mutual benefits for business and society when aligned with strategic objectives (Aakhus & Bzdak, 2012). Employees from private enterprises particularly emphasized the reputation-enhancing and customer loyalty aspects of CSR, consistent with previous studies highlighting CSR's marketing and branding significance in competitive industries (Mabkhot & Piaralal, 2023).

Perceived Motivations Behind CSR

Employees' perceptions of the underlying motivations driving CSR efforts provide critical insight into organizational authenticity and credibility. The study found a distinct split in perceptions between legal compliance and sustainable development as primary motivators. In public sector enterprises such as RINL and HPCL, employees predominantly viewed CSR as an obligation stemming from government regulation and social accountability. The influence of the Companies Act, 2013, was particularly evident, as many respondents associated CSR activities with mandated compliance rather than voluntary strategic initiatives. CSR was thus perceived as part of the organization's public duty and ethical governance rather than a source of competitive differentiation.

On contrary, employees in private sector organizations such as Divi's Laboratories and Coromandel International interpreted CSR as a strategic and value-driven activity. Divi's Laboratories stressed on motivations based on innovation, long-term sustainability and brand reputation. Integration of CSR into corporate strategy has increased to stakeholder relations and strengthen market positioning. The analysis reveals, with obtained statistical values ($\beta = 0.222$, $p < 0.01$) and involvement ($\beta = 0.251$, $p < 0.01$), a positive relationship between CSR motivation and both awareness. It establishes the fact that as employees become more aware and engaged, they are more likely to perceive CSR as strategically motivated rather than merely compliant or philanthropic. The analysis supports the theoretical difference between legal, ethical, and strategic dimensions of CSR, suggesting that organizational culture and communication significantly shape how employees interpret CSR approach.

Statistical Results

The relationship between employee characteristics and their influence on awareness, involvement, perception, and motivation toward CSR in public and private sector enterprises is provided by the following statistical analysis.

Table 1. Summary of Descriptive Statistics on CSR Awareness, Involvement, Strategic Perception, and Motivation

Variable	Mean (Public)	Mean (Private)	Std. Deviation	Key Observation
CSR Awareness	3.78	4.21	0.64	Higher awareness in private sector employees
CSR Involvement	3.66	4.10	0.59	Private firms show more employee participation
Perceived Strategic Impact	3.89	4.25	0.62	CSR seen as reputation-building, especially in private sector
CSR Motivation	3.72	4.08	0.60	Private: strategic intent; Public: compliance/philanthropy

Table 2. ANOVA Summary – Differences in CSR Awareness, Involvement, and Perception by Demographic Factors

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	F-Value	Significance (p)	Interpretation
CSR Awareness	Education	5.87	0.000**	Significant difference; higher education = higher awareness
CSR Awareness	Work Experience	4.31	0.002**	Experienced employees show better CSR understanding
CSR Involvement	Sector	7.55	0.001**	Private sector more involved than public sector

CSR Involvement	Income	3.94	0.008**	Higher income correlates with greater involvement
Perceived Strategic Impact	Managerial Cadre	6.42	0.000**	Managers more likely to link CSR to organizational success
CSR Motivation	Sector	8.16	0.000**	Sector-based divergence: strategic (private) vs. compliance (public)

Note: *p < 0.05 significant; **p < 0.01 highly significant

Table 3. Multiple Regression Analysis – Predictors of CSR Perception and Involvement

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	Beta (β)	t-Value	Sig. (p)	Interpretation
CSR Involvement	CSR Awareness	0.432	6.78	0.000**	Awareness strongly predicts involvement
CSR Involvement	Education	0.215	3.52	0.001**	Higher education → higher engagement
CSR Strategic Impact	CSR Involvement	0.435	7.11	0.000**	Engagement enhances perceived strategic impact
CSR Strategic Impact	Experience	0.263	4.08	0.000**	Experienced employees perceive CSR as strategic
CSR Motivation	Awareness	0.222	3.89	0.001**	Informed employees attribute strategic motives to CSR
CSR Motivation	Involvement	0.251	4.26	0.000**	Active involvement reinforces belief in strategic CSR

Model Summary:

- Adjusted R² (CSR Involvement Model): 0.378
- Adjusted R² (CSR Strategic Impact Model): 0.412
- Adjusted R² (CSR Motivation Model): 0.354
- Overall Model Significance (F-test): p < 0.001

These results confirm that awareness, education, and experience are consistent predictors of CSR perception and participation, explaining between 35–41% of the variance in employee engagement outcomes.

The condensed results collectively validate the following major relationships:

1. Sectoral Variation:

Employees in private sector organizations demonstrate significantly higher awareness, involvement, and belief in CSR’s strategic importance compared to public sector employees.

2. Education and Experience:

Educational qualification and years of experience emerged as the most consistent demographic predictors of positive CSR perception. This suggests that informed and seasoned employees are better equipped to recognize CSR’s organizational value.

3. CSR Awareness → Involvement → Strategic Impact:

Regression models reveal a sequential relationship, where higher awareness fosters greater involvement, which in turn strengthens the perception of CSR’s strategic benefits. This validates the internal stakeholder engagement model proposed by Freeman (1984) (Fassin, 2009) and empirically supports the strategic CSR framework (Porter & Kramer, 2006).

4. **Motivational Orientation:**

The distinction between compliance-driven and strategic CSR orientation is evident across sectors. Public sector employees emphasize legal and ethical motivations, while private sector employees highlight innovation, brand image, and stakeholder value as core drivers.

This analysis affirms that CSR effectiveness is not only determined by financial allocation but also by how deeply employees participate in CSR processes. It also illustrates that CSR involvement and awareness are two interdependent factors of motivation and perceived strategic impact. Private organizations should ensure inclusiveness and authenticity in CSR initiatives to maintain engagement and credibility.

Discussion

The findings of the study can be discussed on the following broader areas:

Theoretical Implications

This study validates the principles of stakeholder theory by demonstrating that employees, as internal stakeholders, play an important role in shaping CSR outcomes. These outcomes depend on external stakeholder satisfaction along with internal alignment of employee values and perceptions with corporate goals. The study also reinforces the CSR pyramid, which integrates economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities, illustrating how employee understanding spans these dimensions differently across sectors. It also establishes the strategic CSR framework, which argues that CSR generates shared value when embedded into business strategy rather than treated as peripheral compliance. The employees in public sector organizations exemplify legal and moral aspects while those in private sectors stressed on strategic orientation. These variations emphasize the contextual and cultural dynamics of CSR interpretation within organizations.

Managerial Implications

From a managerial perspective, the findings suggest that employee engagement is the cornerstone of effective CSR implementation. Organizations must invest in internal communication, training, and participatory mechanisms to cultivate awareness and a sense of ownership among employees. CSR should be integrated into corporate culture through transparent communication, volunteer programs, and performance recognition systems that link social contributions with professional development.

For public sector enterprises, the key challenge lies in transitioning from a compliance-oriented mindset to a strategic CSR culture. Leadership should emphasize the long-term business and societal value of CSR and encourage bottom-up participation. Initiatives such as employee-driven CSR committees, feedback channels, and collaborative project design can enhance involvement and reshape perceptions.

For private sector organizations, the implication is to sustain authenticity and avoid over-commercialization of CSR. Employees can detect when CSR efforts are primarily publicity-driven, which can undermine credibility. Managers should therefore focus on aligning CSR projects with employee values and community needs, fostering a sense of purpose and social identity within the workforce.

Policy and Practical Implications

From a policy standpoint, the findings suggest that government and corporate regulators should recognize employee inclusion as a key performance indicator in CSR reporting. The current compliance framework under the Companies Act, 2013, focuses primarily on expenditure rather than employee participation or awareness. Introducing guidelines that encourage employee engagement metrics could enhance CSR's internal legitimacy and overall impact.

Conclusion

This study establishes that employee perception is a decisive factor in determining CSR's strategic success. CSR transcends its regulatory and philanthropic boundaries to become a driver of ethical business conduct and sustainable growth when employees are informed, engaged, and motivated. The internal stakeholder dimension, highlighting the interplay between awareness, involvement and perception shapes CSR outcomes. A participatory, inclusive and value-driven internal culture is essential to improve CSR impact. CSR fully evolves from a mandated practice to a transformative force for both business and society only when it is perceived as a part of professional identity by the employees.

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